

Forest ecosystem services and the well-being of communities: a case of non-wood forest products in remote areas of the highlands in Scotland and the Ukrainian Carpathians

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This paper explores practical issues of the contribution of non-wood forest products and services (NWFPs & S) to sustainable development (SD) of remote mountain areas. Literature reviews on the topic formed the start of our research. Their findings show that NWFPs & S are generally considered to be particularly important for rural communities living in marginalised areas, such as mountains, where local well-being is usually lower than in more accessible regions. We test this hypothesis, and using participatory techniques in combination of mixed-methods, analyse existing similarities and differences between the contribution of NWFPs & S to rural communities' well-being in Scottish uplands and the Ukraine's Carpathians. Results provide evidence that in the Ukrainian Carpathians, forest-dependent communities heavily rely on forest products and amenities. Local people primarily collect and use wild berries and mushrooms, but they also utilise birch sap, wild honey, herbs, etc. At times, they collect more NWFPs than they are capable to consume, and earn money by selling these. Remote mountain communities are also very much dependent upon the supporting ecosystem services. Forest also contributes to the sense of identity of many community members. Forest land is used for grassing and recreation, which is also typical for Scotland. In Scotland, NWFPs which are sold unprocessed include wild mushrooms, moss and bulbs. Most commonly used wild woodland products include: wild food, honey and bee products, herbs, and wood products used for beverages, as firewood, in orchards, basket production and crafts. Among the cultivated NWFPs, berries and honey play a part in both the economy and the traditional image of Scotland. Sport hunting and fishing are popular. However, the resource base available for NWFPs in Scotland is relatively small (to compare with that in Ukraine) and forest management almost never takes NWFPs into account. Recent policy documents highlight the importance of enabling rural communities to choose their own priorities and solutions. Supporting local people to work on these appropriate solutions is deemed to enhance ecosystems resilience and sustainability of NWFP & S production, management and use. However, there are many challenges in the field, observed both in the Scottish highlands and the Carpathian Mountains, including of how to attain a proper balance between NWFPs and wood production, as economically timber is still the most important resource provided by forests in both countries, while there is an increasing demand for NWFPs & S. Also, to protect the interests of forest dependent communities, their priorities and concerns in term of forest multiple ecosystem services need to be identified and included into the

forest management planning. Recommendations for sustainable management of natural resources need to be developed by involving in the decision-making processes of all relevant stakeholder groups (e.g. through the creation of active groups). Commercialization and value-added processing of NWFPs, as a way to improve the contribution to household income, should be explored; while sustainable harvesting of NWFPs may find a niche role in sustainable development of remote localities through ecotourism. It is also important to increase environmental awareness in society and to strive for cohesion and social innovation in marginalised rural areas, which are largely represented in these countries by remote mountain regions. This study was supported by the COST Action FP1203: European Non-Wood Forest Products in frame of the EU Framework Programme Horizon 2020.